

Parameters for Evaluating an IRS

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Introduction :

Evaluation is a process of feedback against an investment in time, energy, money, knowledge and intelligence. Evaluation usually results in indicators that gauge the usefulness of systems and services. Information storage and retrieval systems are evaluated from viewpoints such as users, economy, coverage, hardware, software, man-power, environmental conditions, etc.

An evaluation study can be conducted from two different points of view. When it is conducted from managerial point of view, the evaluation study is called management-oriented; conducted from users' point of view it is called a user-oriented evaluation study. Many information scientists advocate that an evaluation of information retrieval system should always be user-oriented, i.e. evaluators should pay more attention to those factors that can provide improved service to the users.

Parameters for Evaluating an IRS :

Evaluating an information retrieval (IR) system involves measuring how effectively and efficiently it retrieves relevant information for users. **Effectiveness** and **Efficiency** are **two basic parameters** for measuring the performance of system. They are as follows:

1. Effectiveness :

Effectiveness means the level up to which the given system attained its objectives. Thus, in information retrieval system effectiveness may be measure of how far it can retrieve relevant information while with-holding non-relevant information.

2. Efficiency :

Efficiency means how economically the system is achieving its objectives. In an information retrieval system efficiency can be measured by factors such as cost. The cost factors are to be calculated indirectly. They include factors as response time, time taken by the system to provide an answer.

Other Parameters for Evaluating an IRS :

Other parameters for evaluating an IRS will be-

1. Usability :

Usability is a measure that embraces the interface through which the user interacts with the system, and also takes into account the user and their expectations, skills and experiences.

2. Satisfaction :

There is no agreed definition of user satisfaction within the information science and information system communities. The original proponents of user satisfaction as a criterion for IR system evaluation assumed that it was correlated with search success. Applegate outlines three different models of searcher satisfaction namely:

- The material satisfaction model
- The emotional satisfaction- simple path model
- The emotional satisfaction- multiple path model

Search result would be an appropriate measure of the material satisfaction model. Both emotional satisfaction models are based upon subjective impressions and assessments which may be affected by factors such as:

- Search task
- Search setting
- The searcher's state contributes to quality and satisfaction judgments in digital environments
- Other perspectives on satisfaction are to be found in the service quality and website quality literatures.

3. Cost :

Users may experience costs in terms of any payment that they need to make for system or document access but the most significant cost is associated with the time that they expend in searching a system. Search algorithm, the options for the display of hits, the seamlessness of the stages in individual systems and interoperability between systems.

4. Recall : The term recall refers to a measure of whether or not a particular item is retrieved or the extent to which the retrieval of wanted items occurs. Recall

thus relates to the ability of the system to retrieve relevant documents. Therefore,

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Numbers of relevant items retrieved}}{\text{Total number of relevant items in the collection}} \times 100$$

5. Precision : Precision means how precisely a particular system functions. It relates to its ability not to retrieve non-relevant documents; i.e. the non-relevant items are discarded by the user. Therefore,

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Numbers of relevant items retrieved}}{\text{Total number of items retrieved}} \times 100$$

6. Time lag :

The average interval between the time the search request is made and the time an answer is provided. In context to this we can say that response time is the average time needed to obtain a response from the system. It depends on organization of stored documents, type of query, location of information centre, frequency of receiving user's queries and the size of the collection.

7. User effort :

It is intellectual as well as physical, required from the user in obtaining answers to the search requests. It depends on accessibility of the system, availability of guidance by system personnel, volume of retrieved items and facilities for interaction with the system.

8. Form of presentation :

The form of the search output, which affects the user's ability to make use of the retrieved items; i.e. the form in which search results are presented to the user. It depends on type of display device and nature of output – bibliographic reference, abstract, or full text.

9. Collection coverage :

It is the extent to which the system includes relevant matter. It depends on type of input device and type and size of storage device, depth of subject analysis,

nature of users' demand, nature of core subject area, physical forms of documents.

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